

Synthesis of Nitrate Complexes of Lanthanum(III) with Schiff Bases derived from 4-Antipyrinecarboxaldehyde and Aromatic Amines

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The biological activities¹ and coordination chemistry^{2,3} of 2/3-pyrazolin-5-ones have been studied. A few reports on Schiff bases derived from 4-acyl-3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazoline-5-one and their metal complexes are available in the literature⁴. In an earlier communication⁵ we reported the synthesis of Schiff bases derived from 4-antipyrinecarboxaldehyde (4-formyl-2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolin-5-one) and their Ni^{II} complexes. Here we report the nitrate complexes of lanthanum(III) with the Schiff bases (1-8) derived from 4-antipyrinecarboxaldehyde and *o*-, *p*- and *m*-anisidine, *o*-, *p*- and *m*-toluidine, 2,6- or 2,4-xylylidine.

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|---|--------------|
| 1; R = -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ (<i>o</i>) | (ANTC-OA) |
| 2; R = -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ (<i>p</i>) | (ANTC-PA) |
| 3; R = -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ (<i>m</i>) | (ANTC-MA) |
| 4; R = -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (<i>o</i>) | (ANTC-OT) |
| 5; R = -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (<i>p</i>) | (ANTC-PT) |
| 6; R = -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (<i>m</i>) | (ANTC-MT) |
| 7; R = -C ₆ H ₃ (CH ₃) ₂ (2,6) | (ANTC-2,6-X) |
| 8; R = -C ₆ H ₃ (CH ₃) ₂ (2,4) | (ANTC-2,4-X) |

Results and Discussion

The Schiff bases (1-8) form the 7-coordinate complexes of general formula [La(L-L)₂(NO₃)₃] when refluxed with lanthanum(III) nitrate in ethanol. All the complexes (Table 1) are non-hygroscopic solids, moderately soluble in methanol, dimethylformamide, acetonitrile and nitrobenzene, and insoluble in carbon tetrachloride, chloroform and petroleum ether. The electrical conductance values (5.8-10.3 Ω⁻¹ cm⁻¹ mol⁻¹) suggest that they are non-electrolytes and the molecular weights reveal their monomeric nature. As expected, they are all diamagnetic.

Ir spectral band at 1 600 cm⁻¹ (ring C=O) of the Schiff base ligands shifted to lower wavenumbers and appeared around 1 560 cm⁻¹ in the complexes. This suggests coordination of ring carbonyl oxygen² to lanthanum in these complexes. All the Schiff base ligands showed a sharp band at ~1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=N) which shifted to lower energy by 12-30 cm⁻¹ on complexation due to the reduction in the electron density in the azomethine link on account of coordination to the metal ions⁵. The two medium bands at around 1 440 and 1 320 cm⁻¹ present in the spectra of the complexes, are assigned to ν₄ and ν₁ vibration respectively, of the coordinated nitrate ion. Since the difference between ν₄ and ν₁ is of the order of ~120 cm⁻¹, the nitrate ions tentatively suggested to be monodentate in these complexes⁶.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES*

Compd.	Empirical formula	La% : Found/ (Calcd.)
[La(ANTC-OA) ₂ (NO ₃) ₃]	C ₃₈ H ₃₈ N ₉ O ₁₃ La	14.02 (14.37)
[La(ANTC-PA) ₂ (NO ₃) ₃]	C ₃₈ H ₃₈ N ₉ O ₁₃ La	14.14 (14.37)
[La(ANTC-MA) ₂ (NO ₃) ₃]	C ₃₈ H ₃₈ N ₉ O ₁₃ La	14.52 (14.37)
[La(ANTC-OT) ₂ (NO ₃) ₃]	C ₃₈ H ₃₈ N ₉ O ₁₃ La	14.63 (14.86)
[La(ANTC-PT) ₂ (NO ₃) ₃]	C ₃₈ H ₃₈ N ₉ O ₁₃ La	14.95 (14.86)
[La(ANTC-MT) ₂ (NO ₃) ₃]	C ₃₈ H ₄₈ N ₉ O ₁₃ La	14.59 (14.86)
[La(ANTC-2,6-X) ₂ (NO ₃) ₃]	C ₄₀ H ₄₂ N ₉ O ₁₁ La	14.12 (14.43)
[La(ANTC-2,4-X) ₂ (NO ₃) ₃]	C ₄₀ H ₄₂ N ₉ O ₁₁ La	14.62 (14.43)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

The electronic spectra of the Schiff bases exhibit two bands at 36 500-37 100 and 40 100-40 950 cm⁻¹ due to the n → π* and π → π* transitions respectively. These two bands are also present in the spectra of the complexes but appear at lower wavenumbers at 33 900-35 200 and 36 800-38 200 cm⁻¹ respectively. The spectra of the complexes show an additional band at 25 900-26 900 cm⁻¹ which is attributed to the L → M charge transfer transition.

The exact geometries of the present complexes can be ascertained only by X-ray diffraction studies on single crystals which is not available.

Experimental

Lanthanum(III) nitrate hexahydrate (B.D.H.), *o*-, *m*- and *p*-anisidine, 4-antipyrinecarboxaldehyde, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-anisidine (Aldrich), *o*-, *m*- and *p*-toluidine (Sarabhai M. Chemicals), 2,4- and 2,6-xylydines (SFF, Dottikon, Switzerland) were used as supplied.

The Schiff bases (1–8) were prepared⁸ by refluxing a mixture of 4-antipyrinecarboxaldehyde (0.01 mol) and the appropriate amine (0.01 mol) in ethanol.

The complexes separated as orange crystals when $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2 mmol in 25 ml ethanol) was refluxed with the Schiff base (4 mmol in ~100 ml ethanol) for 5–6 h and the resulting mixture concentrated to a small volume. The solid complexes were washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure over silica gel (yields 65–69%).

The lanthanum content of the complexes was determined by the oxalate-oxide method as reported elsewhere⁹. C, H and N analyses were performed microanalytically.

The electrical conductance (DMF) was measured at room temperature using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 457 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (DMF) on a Beckman

DU spectrophotometer. Molecular weight was determined by Rast's method¹⁰ using biphenyl as solvent.

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